

Condition of Labour Class in 17th Century India

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Labour is the most important factor of production even today. Neither the development of science and technology nor the sophistication of modern automation has been able to establish a perfect substitute of labour. Labour was all pervading because everything from biggest to the smallest operation was performed by the ingenuity of human labour. In the 16th and 17th centuries industrial organization was broadly organized on two patterns. One was the artisan or cottage system and other was the karkhana system. Under the artisan system the artisans, possessing little resource, worked at home on their own initiative, from the raw material to the marketing stage. At times they worked to order of foreign merchants or their brokers with advances of money. Under the karkhana system the artisans seemed to exchange freedom for security. They worked under strict regimentation and to dictation as day labourers from morning to evening. According to Bernier, 'The artisans repair every morning to their respective karkhanas where they remain employed the whole day and in the evening return to their homes'.¹ The accounts of Hawkins, Pelsaert and De Laet to the effect that a work done by a single European worker would be done by three or four Indian labours² might mean either that the efficiency of the latter compared unfavourably with the Europeans or that there was excessive specialization. The absence of private factories by artisans in the 17th century was not due to 'want of genius' among Indians, as according to Bernier there were 'ingenious men in every part of the Indies'.³

The major factor that induced the artisans to secure employment in the state karkhanas was the deplorable condition of the artisans who worked independently of their own. The lot of the labourers was not happy nor conducive to the true economic development of the country. At the capital which was the largest and richest city in the land, there were no private factories, no workshops owned and managed by skilful artisans on their own behalf. As Bernier rightly observes, "If the artists and manufacturers were encouraged, the useful and fine arts would flourish; but these unhappy men are condemned, treated with harshness, and inadequately remunerated for their labour. The rich will have article at a cheap rate. When an Omrah or Mansabdar requires the services of an artisan, he sends to the bazar for him, employing force, if necessary, to make the poor man work; and after the task is finished, the unfeeling lord pays, not according to the value of the labour, but agreeably to his own standard of fair remuneration; the artisan having reason to congratulate himself if the korrah (lash) has not been given in part payment. How then can it be expected that any spirit of emulation should animate the artist or manufacturer? Instead of contending for a superiority of reputation, his only anxiety is to finish his work, and to earn the pittance that shall supply him with a piece of bread. The artists, therefore, who arrive at any eminence in their art are those only who are in the service of the King or of some powerful Omrah, and who work exclusively for their patron".⁴

The caste organisation was itself a training ground for the artisans. Various occupations were hereditary as castes were the representatives of the various crafts. From father to son, by heredity and family training, the skill in the artist was handed down. In the days of the Mughals we find no mention of the existence of schools and colleges for the training of arts and crafts. Very ably Pelsaert sums up labour in Jehangir's India. He says, 'Workman's children can follow no occupation other than that of their father, nor can they intermarry with any other caste'.⁵ "The embroiderer brings up his son as an embroiderer", says Bernier, "a goldsmith's son becomes a goldsmith and a physician of the city educates his son for a physician. No one marries but in his own caste and profession, and this custom is observed almost rigidly by the Mohammedans as by the gentile to whom It is expressly enjoined by the law".⁶

Information about the economic position of artisans is extremely scanty. We get a few incidental details from the memoirs of Babur and the *Ain-i- Akbari* and some observations of a few foreign travellers. Babur alludes in his memoirs to the 'unnumbered and endless workmen of every kind', infinite number of artisans in different crafts and industries as one of the advantages of Hindustan.⁷ Abul Fazl speaks of 'skilful masters and craftsmen' having settled in the country. He also mentions the wages of unskilled and skilled labourers of different categories.⁸

With regard to urban labour in Mughal India, European history records and accounts of foreign travellers illustrate the extent of coercion, official or nonofficial, on the artisans, skilled or unskilled. Pelsaert, chief of the Dutch factory at Agra observes on the basis of the seven years' experience that 'there were three classes of people who were indeed nominally free but whose status differs little from voluntary slavery : workmen, peons, or servants and small shopkeepers'. Again, 'For the workmen there are two scourges, first of which is low wages. Goldsmith, painters, embroiderers, carpet- makers, weavers; by working from morning to night can earn only 5 or 6 tanckas; or about 1/5th of a rupee'. This is also corroborated by De Laet and some other foreign travellers.⁹ After referring to the first scourge of low wages, Pelsaert writes, "The second scourge is (the oppression of) the Governor, the nobles, the Diwan, the Kotwal, the Bakhshi, and other royal officers. If any of these wants a workman, the man is not asked if he is willing to come, but is seized in the house or in the street, well beaten if he should dare to raise any objection, and in the evening paid half his wages, or nothing at all".¹⁰

Some of the European companies not only employed slave labour but also resorted to forced labour. The Dutch and English hired many Indian artisans in various capacities in different places, e.g., as weavers of cotton and silk, bleachers, printers, coopers, blacksmiths, etc. Early in 17th century the Dutch resorted to forced labour by engaging 200-300 cloth printers and bleachers at Pulicat. In the seventies of the 17th century the Dutch engaged in their workshops at Hugli the Indian weavers manufacturing sail cloth or producing ropes, who were paid 'small wage', from 1 to 2 annas daily. During the sixties and seventies of the 17th century the English hired on a monthly wage basis, Indian yarn- twisters, weavers, printers, dyers, etc., besides brokers and treasurers through whom advance (*dadán*) was given to artisans or local merchants.¹¹ Another adverse factor for artisans was the middleman's share. According to Mandeslo, both craftsman and merchants had a very unhappy time; the craftsman, because the same piece of work passed through a large number of hands on its way to the consumer, with the consequence that the craftsman had to relinquish to middlemen a large proportion of the profits of his industry.¹² This seems to be corroborated by Bernier when he continues his observations on the artisan: 'He never can become rich, and he feels it no trifling matter if he have the means of satisfying the cravings of hunger and of covering his body with the coarsest garment. If money be gained, it does not in any measure go into his pocket, but only serves to increase the wealth of the merchant'.¹³

All this created an uneconomic outlook on the parts of artisans. The masses could, because of poverty, exercise no effective demand on production of goods of superior workmanship. They wanted cheap necessities of life. Fear of oppression led to concealment of wealth and permanent inurement to a low standard. Bernier writes: "No artist can be expected to give his mind to his calling in the midst of a people who are either wretchedly poor, or who, if rich, assume an appearance of poverty, and who regard not the beauty and excellence, but the cheapness of an article : a people whose grandees pay for a work of art considerably under its value, and according to their own caprice, and who do not hesitate to punish an importunate artist, or tradesman, with the *korrah*".¹⁴

The nobles who directly or indirectly appropriated an enormous share of the trading profits threw also on the commercial exploitation on the artisans. The class of the nobles which was controlling the state machine, could use so powerful an instrument of exploitation as the taxation system. Thus high taxes on Hindus under Aurangzeb at the end of the 17th century, and

the persecution of 'infidels' in general became the state policy during that period and inflicted a heavy blow on the crafts and commerce in the country. The system of state monopolies on the production or purchase of certain goods (saltpetre, dyes, salt, diamond etc.) enabled the officials of the state and some nobles and also merchants or nobles to oppress the artisans in many ways. The arbitrary rule of the nobles, extended to many spheres of the artisan's economic and political life. The rulers could resettle large group of artisans to newly built towns, suburbs, etc.¹⁵

At the beginning of the 17th century in Golconda the artisans were compelled to pay somewhat to the governor where they live, or do his work gratis. Bernier wrote, 'that the jagirdars, governors, or contractors, have an authority almost absolute over the peasantry, and nearly as much over the artisans and merchants of the towns and villages within their district; and nothing can be imagined more cruel and oppressive than the manner in which it is exercised'.¹⁶ He wrote that this was one of the main reasons responsible for the decline of commerce and crafts in Mughal empire in the second half of the 17th century.

Speaking of labour's efficiency under state patronage Abul Fazl in his Ain has referred to the care and attention bestowed by the King upon the manufacture of various stuffs in the state Karkhanajats. The karkhanajats, the imperial workshops and the cities of Lahore, Agra, Fatehpur, Ahmedabad made skilful products of art in a variety of fashions which astonished foreign travellers. His Majesty personally acquired all necessary theoretical and practical knowledge of the existing arts and the workman considerably improved. Hand-weaving and silk spinning were improved and the imperial workshops furnished articles manufactured in European, Iranian and Mongolian countries. "A taste for fine material became general, and the drapery used at feasts surpassed every description".¹⁷ Jadunath Sarkar rightly maintained that Masulipatam in the Golconda kingdom was the home of many artisans skilled in calico printing and many letters of Aurangzeb, then Viceroy of the Deccan, exhibit his ardent desire to send some of the artists to the state factories of Agra and Delhi. This was practically forced labour.¹⁸

The prosperity of the artisans was directly linked to the growth of the market; and Mughal India did not witness any upward mobility of the artisans due to mercantile profit. Occupational mobility was quite limited; in rare cases the agriculturist at best moved to weaving, and there was some horizontal mobility among a few occupations, such as carpenters, goldsmith and stonemasons. The rural producers sometimes moved to the local centres of production. Regional mobility was restricted due to the local caste inhibitions, as is evident from the failure of the English to bring weavers from Kashimbazar to Madras via Hugli.¹⁹

During Mughal period there were two types of labour - (i) skilled labour (ii) unskilled labour. Skilled labour formed an important basis of urban life. The artisans served as the productive base of urban economic life, his products constituted one of the chief sources through which the towns could eventually acquire an independent economic status. Towns and cities played an important role in the growth of manufacturers. The number and size of towns and cities increased during the 13th and 14th centuries in northern India. For much of the central as well as northern India the 16th and 17th centuries became 'a veritable golden age' of urbanization. It has been suggested that urban population in the Mughal Empire rose to 15 per cent of the total. The growth of towns and cities with their vertical linkage in different parts of the country and their horizontal linkage all over the subcontinent encouraged trade as well as manufacturer.²⁰

Rapid development of towns was responsible for the increasing numbers of artisans. Agra, Delhi, Ahmedabad, Surat, Dacca, Baroda etc. were important centres of production. Textile industry was one of the most important industry of medieval India. Indian weavers were proficient in the art of weaving all kinds of clothes.²¹ Besides weavers, carpenters also exhibited their excellence in making ships, boats, etc. In cities they were busy in making boats and ships and in villages they fulfilled the demands of the peasants. After the establishment of English

company they came into contact with Europeans and learned the new techniques of making ships, boats. So well that they excelled the Europeans.²² Goldsmiths and silversmiths also made beautiful ornaments. Manucci says, "The goldsmiths are almost continuously busy with the making of ornaments. The best and most costly of their productions are for the king's person, the queens and the princesses."²³

The blacksmith was very vital to every village community. He made the ploughshares, hoes and axes. The armour industry provided a major source of demand for the services of the smiths. With the help of their primitive tools they could imitate anything. Shoes were not commonly used by the masses. It was an article of use by a certain privileged class of the society. Leather workers made shoes with gold and silver work upon them. Masons were also employed in the construction of forts, Mahals and other important buildings.²⁴ Percy Brown is of the view that the local guilds of masons who were freed from the restraints of their old and indigenous conventions were mainly responsible for the inventive formation and fresh spirit of the notable architectural synthesis.²⁵

We discussed the condition and plight of skilled labourers in Mughal India. If we review the condition of unskilled labourers, we find that their plight was worse than the skilled ones. The former did not have any special skill for which they had to do manual labour and to get very low wages. Unskilled labour was employed for personal services some were free and some slaves, but in both of the cases the functions or duties were the same, and could be interchanged. Abul Fazl notes in the Ain that more than 5000 ladies were in Akbar's Palace, all had their respective apartment and were attended to by adequate number of servants, female guards and eunuchs. The Imperial camp employed between 2000 to 3000 servants, and for each type of work more than the required number of servants were employed. Moreland gives a detailed discussion on servants at the time of Akbar.²⁶

During the Mughal period there was in India a considerable variety of arts and handicrafts which, indeed, exhibited a more advanced economic and financial organisation than the crafts in contemporary Europe. In the first place, in several handicrafts the specialisation of tasks advanced to the extent that particular groups of artisans came to undertake distinct processes in the chain of production. Such integration and coordination of production were hardly reached in European handicrafts. Secondly, there were whole villages and muhallas of cities and towns which devoted themselves to production of specialised products, whether cotton or silk fabric, gold, silver and brass manufacture, bidri work, or ivory, to mention only a few that commanded both Indian as well as foreign markets. Thirdly, the foreign trade in products of Indian arts and handicrafts developed a corresponding organisation of production, under which master artisans or entrepreneurs brought together groups of artisans who worked for them on the wage basis, and an organisation of trade and finance under which a chain of itinerant intermediaries, including English and Dutch merchants, when they realised the importance of the Indian export trade in calicoes, gave advances to artisans to obtain their products. Artisans worked on their own account as well as in karkhanas, big and small, under master artisans, dealers and financiers.²⁷

In the Mughal Empire there grew up a large variety of state karkhanas for fabricating various kinds of products of handicrafts. The organisation was that craftsmen in different fields of industry were assembled in a karkhana which was placed in charge of a malik over whom there was the State General Superintendent of Arts and Crafts. Bernier gives a description of the factories at work in the Mughal capital: "Large halls are seen in many places, called karkhanas or workshops for the artisans. In one hall embroiderers are busily employed, superintended by a master. In another you see goldsmiths, in a third painters, in a fourth varnishers in lacquer-work, in a fifth joiners, turners, tailors, shoemakers, in a sixth manufacturers of silk, brocade, and those fine muslins of which are made turbans, girdles with

golden flowers, and (the fine) drawers worn by females beautifully embroidered with needle work. Tire artisans repair every morning to their respective workshops, where they remain employed the whole day; and in the evening return to their homes."²⁸ Abul Fazl gives information that Akbar invited a number of master craftsmen from far and wide places and settle them in the cities of northern India.²⁹ Father Monserrate gives the reference of the encouragement of artisans under the patronage of Emperor Akbar. Similarly during the reign of Jahangir and ShahJahan the patronage to the artisans continued.³⁰ Only those artisans were appointed to the court Karkhanas, who were highly skilled and from different part of the countries they were sent to the capital where these skilled artisans were working under the guidance of experts. Pelsaert talks about prince Khurram, 'He was a patron of all craftsmen to whom he paid such high wages that he attracted all the splendour of his father's court'.³¹ Pelsaert again says that the workmen of Agra followed hereditary occupations.

The agricultural labourer was ordinarily a serf, receiving in return for his work an amount of commodities determined by customs and about sufficient to keep him and his family alive. The village artisan was also supported by customary payments. It was only in the towns and cities that men were hired and the rate of wages can be said to have existed. We find that there was already a drift from the villages towards cities in the beginning of medieval India. Bernier said that this drift had become important at the period when he visited India. He writes thus: "...that many of the peasantry driven to despair by so execrable a tyranny, abandon the country and seek a more tolerable mode of existence either in the towns or in camps".³²

Some light is thrown on the position of the most important class of artisans by the experience furnished by the Gujarat famine of 1630-31. At this period Gujarat had benefited by the expansion of trade resulting from the appearance of foreign buyers in the markets, and it is reasonable to suppose that the weavers and workers in allied industries were at least as prosperous as their fellows in other parts of India. Their economic position was, however, unsatisfactory when judged by the familiar test of resistance to the stress of famine, for contemporary accounts show the complete collapse of the industrial organisation. By November 1630 the weavers and other artisans had abandoned their homes in such numbers that cargo for the English ships could not be procured, and when rain fell in the following June the merchants found it necessary to dole out grain to the weavers at Broach and Baroda, a "serf of corn" being given for each piece of cloth delivered.³³

Two factors in particular - the cost of materials and the burden of taxation may be noticed as having probably exercised a material influence conducing to this result. The cost of metals was high, and consequently the metal-worker without sufficient capital would be entirely in the hands of whoever might provide him with material. In Northern India at least the price of raw cotton was also high, for in the revenue assessment the crop was charged with rates which indicate that it was much more valuable than wheat, and where this relation held, the strength of the middleman or financier was obviously greater than now.³⁴

In conclusion it may be stated that the standard of living of the labour population was on the margin of bare subsistence. The working conditions of labours make it clear that there was practically no scope for the working population to lead a peaceful and a comfortable life. They could not think of living in peace and comfort except for distress which was aggravated further by the high-handedness of the State officials.

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